

Disability-focused Christianity for Palestinians

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This group includes the many Christian-based NGOs and parachurch ministries in Bethlehem that are providing services for people with disabilities. Most institutes employ Muslims as well as Christians but are Christian in name and practice. Most of the Christians, then, belong to recognized churches in addition to this group. I conducted 12 months of ethnographic fieldwork with two NGOs in Bethlehem providing services for people with (primarily intellectual) disabilities (May 2021- May 2022). Most of the data in this article is based on my primary methods of participant observation and semi-structured interviews. Over this time I visited 12 different organizations and interviewed their staff. While each NGO is organizationally separate, they are unified by friendships of varying closeness (and some familiar ties), a shared purpose in improving the lives of people with disabilities in the region, and in some cases, the same people receiving services (some simultaneously and others at different times). Some of the staff have rotated between the organizations as well. Another feature that unifies this group is the relatively marginal support they receive from local churches. Most individuals are connected with the major denominations, regularly attending a Catholic, Orthodox, or Lutheran church, but a lot of support (emotional, financial, staffing) comes from international churches or non-church Palestinian institutions, like local universities. Collegiate special education programs provide regular and reliable volunteers for several of these organizations as students complete their practical training. Something that distinguishes this group from other members of the same denominations is their understanding and practice of inter-faith dialogue. Along with other interfaith initiatives in the West Bank and Bethlehem in particular, these disability-related organizations demonstrate a high-level of collaboration, as will be detailed more in the qualitative notes of this entry. While small numerically, this group is important to consider because of the disproportional impact it has on its community. See the primary source, "Mapping of Christian Organizations in Palestine: Social and Economic Impact" (George Akroush). As Bethlehem has developed and urbanized, it has become a hub of services for Palestinians, medical and otherwise. There are significantly fewer resources available for people living in the villages surrounding Bethlehem, and some will even come from the villages of Hebron and Ramallah to receive services. While growing, the organizations as a whole still struggle to provide all of the services needed.

Date Range: 2012 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Bethlehem, the West Bank

Region tags: Palestine

Bethlehem is a city in the occupied Palestinian territories (oPt, the West Bank).

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Faith in the Face of Empire: The Bible Through Palestinian Eyes (Mitri Raheb)

– Source 2: Quiet Resistance: Living with disability in a Palestinian Refugee Camp and Other Tales of Tenacity (Alice Merrill)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL:

<https://www.daralkalima.edu.ps/uploads/files/Mapping%20of%20Christian%20Organizations%204Final.pdf>

– Source 1 Description: This source lists the Christian-related NGOs providing services to people with disabilities in the West Bank

– Source 2 URL:

<https://www.daralkalima.edu.ps/uploads/files/Mapping%20of%20Christian%20Organizations%204Final.pdf>

– Source 2 Description: Disability-related statistics published by the Palestinian Authority

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.al-monitor.com/originals/2022/08/welcome-palestinians-disabilities-out-front-bethlehem-hotel>

– Source 3 Description: Information about one organization recently employing people with disabilities

– Source 1 URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20100415005256/http://www.al-bushra.org/holyland/sabella.htm>

– Source 1 Description: Statistics on Christians in the Holy Land

– Source 2 URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20150811101759/http://en.lpj.org/2014/10/21/palestinian-christians-in-the-holy-land-and-the-diaspora/>

– Source 2 Description: Qualitative description of challenges facing Christians in the Holy Land

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.qader.org/resources/973.html>

– Source 1 Description: Gender and disability based violence in the West Bank (2019)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: No, these organizations tend to cooperate with their local/ institutional church organizations and hold membership in both groups

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, it is common for members of this group to belong to other religious groups like their local/ institutional churches. Many of the organizations that serve people with disabilities include staff that are Catholic, Orthodox, and Protestant

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: While most of the violence in the region is the result of political tensions between Israelis and Palestinians, it does enter the sample region. There are occasional clashes between families/ tribes, especially related to elections as was the case in April 2022 in the Beit Jala and Bethlehem governates.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, between Israel and Palestine in particular. When Palestinians are killed by Israeli Defense Forces or Israeli settlers, they are considered martyrs in the community. Their home area generally goes on strike the following day. The organizations that serve people with disabilities generally follow the strike, too.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Many people with intellectual disabilities are labeled as such at birth, but they may not formally join this religious group until they are older, depending on their situation and resources

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: The staff of this religious group seek employment voluntarily. About three fourths are women but there are no explicit gender requirements

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: The age can vary. Some organizations serve children starting at a young age while others accept only adults who can be any age over 16 or 18.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Most staff are women but this is not a requirement

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Proselytizing in this group takes the form of educating one's friends and family and other contacts about intellectual disability, combating regional stigma. For example, at the institutions that involve adults, visitors are frequently corrected for referring to the people with intellectual disabilities as children. Organizations strive to create mutual relationships between staff and people with intellectual disability. Many college students will complete internships or volunteer hours at these institutions. This is also a way for them to "share the word" about their organization and the broader network of institutions serving people with intellectual disabilities.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: There is no official political or financial support for this group, to the dismay of many of its members. In many Western countries, welfare supports people with disabilities and can support the institutions which help care for them but no such services are present here. Some say that the government actually makes their work more difficult through bureaucratic challenges

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: While there is no conception of apostasy, there is a general understanding that staff in this line of work ought to stay in it long term. Ideally at the same organization but there are stories of professionals moving between organizations within this sample region, which is tolerated.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 300

Notes: Roughly 300 in the Bethlehem area, including staff and beneficiaries

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.5

Notes: Bethlehem's population is about 30,000, while Beit Sahour and Beit Jala are each about 13,000 people. Each of the organizations fall within these governates but some individual members reside outside of their bounds

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: No official hierarchy between leaders, but there is variation in status between the organizations roughly correlated with their budget and size of impact on the community

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: No, they are hired or were instrumental in founding their organization

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: While there is hierarchy within the organizations, generally people of all levels contribute to decision making. Staff who work most closely with the beneficiaries as well as the members with intellectual disabilities themselves often have unique insight into their organization's needs

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Generally the Christian members adhere to the Old and New Testaments while Muslim members the Holy Qu'ran. There are no other authoritative texts in these groups

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: The architecture of these organizations is not explicitly religious. Most use whatever building they were able to find, often received via international donation. One organization constructed its own

building but not according to a religious style

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: Traditional Iconography generally exists in private spaces of the organization, for example someone's office. Modern iconography exists throughout public spaces, in the form of pictures of members (past and present) or murals, generally created together.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Humans are generally depicted as smiling, wearing regular clothing, in whatever setting they normally inhabit. Some depicted are still alive and others have died. Most take the form of photographs and are not referred to as icons

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Most organizations take regular trips to resorts or camp grounds as they are able to secure funds to do so. The COVID-19 pandemic interrupted this practice between 2020 and 2022 but at the time of writing groups are starting to return. Some of these pilgrimage sites exist in Israel and require members to obtain permission from the State of Israel to attend, which can be difficult. Generally not all members receive permission to travel. Tabagh in Israel is one of these sacred spaces for several of the organizations in Bethlehem, as it includes a German-sponsored camp space designed for people with intellectual disabilities.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Beaches and pools are particularly attractive

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: While members will take pilgrimages to their financial supporters in Europe or local sites in Israel/ Palestine for renewal, they also receive pilgrims in the form of volunteers. They may come for a long period of 3 months or 1-2 years, or 1 week, or even just a day. Many Christian pilgrims come to Bethlehem for the Nativity Church and may also visit this religious group

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: Most members desire to take part but some have difficulty for financial or political reasons as outlined above.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– No

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: During my fieldwork, a person with a disability at one of these organizations died. The FaceBook post commemorating him read, "We belong to God and to God we are returning, with the angels and those next to your Lord" (translated from Arabic)

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Members are buried according to their faith tradition's practice. Muslims are generally buried the day following death, and friends/ loved ones visit during three days of Azzah. Christians may be buried a few days after death in a funeral, with commemorative services after 40 days, 6 months, and 1 year.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: The Christians believe God took the form of a person in Jesus, but not that God is anthropomorphic; Muslims do not believe God is anthropomorphic or takes any human likeness

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: As creator of all things and merciful and benevolent, this group believes that the high God is unquestionably good. All comes from God, disability and otherwise, and God is to be thanked and praised for it

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Some members are motivated to do their work with people with disabilities from a desire to be rewarded in the afterlife for good deeds unable to be repaid in this life.
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Omnipotence, love, omnipresence

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Personal communication through prayer

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Yes but only on rare occasion. Some members have told stories of experiences with angels or of God's guidance in their personal lives

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Angels can interfere with the world to bless members of this and other religious groups

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

Notes: While theoretically possible, I have not heard of any such stories regarding negative emotions among supernatural beings other than God

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but only one: Jesus, most often referred to as the Christ, the Lord, Son of God

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: On rare occasion members may report seeing Jesus but this is not common

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is thought to know the past, present, and future. Despite this region's political instability and unpredictability, members rely on their sense of Jesus' knowledge of the future and capacity to guide them in the present

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:

– No

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in virtue of Jesus' relationship with the Father and membership in the triune High God

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus promises eternal/ abundant life to those who follow him

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus sternly warns against those who do not follow him or treat others with harshness, in particular religious leaders.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

Notes: Jesus would occasionally become angry according to the New Testament, for example with money changers in the Temple. Or, sad in the face of death (eg. his friend Lazarus)

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
– Yes

Notes: For example, after fasting 40 days, Jesus was hungry (Matthew 4, Luke 4)

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

Notes: While there are strong taboos, particularly related to gender norms, discussion about breaking them focuses on social consequences rather than divine

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Implicitly. While it is not discussed, it is understood the murder is wrong

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, sex is tolerated only between married people

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Incest within an immediate family is not tolerated, but marriage between cousins is both tolerated and common. Many comment that one of the reasons for the large number of people with intellectual disabilities in the region is related to consanguineous marriage. Most do not condemn those marriages, but some do lament this aspect of the culture.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Lying is understood to be generally wrong

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: There is an understanding that God cares about people with disabilities and therefore combatting stigma against them which can take the form of converting non-religionists, or people who hold differing views about people with intellectual disabilities

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

Notes: While God does not seem to particularly care, the staff themselves do care about their own and each members' maintenance of personal hygiene

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– No

Notes: The means of punishment are ambiguous

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Many believe that loyalty to this community will lead to reward in the afterlife, especially perseverance through the most challenging moments in this life. Some members express concern about avoiding punishment through good deeds, but the focus is on rewards for good deeds

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: It is uncommon to believe that disability is a result of divine punishment, but many do think of it as random, and some people believe it is a punishment. This is one reason stigma is stigmatized in the broader Bethlehem community

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: Punishment is not talked about frequently. When it is, rarely, it is referred to as a version of hell/ "fire," the details of which are even more rarely discussed in this community.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
– No

Notes: Most members of this community do not explicitly endorse a version of the afterlife that includes reincarnation.

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
– I don't know
Notes: This is a potential, non-necessary form of punishment

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: Some believe that disability or impairment is a result of divine punishment or disfavor. Mostly, though, this community works to correct such theology in the broader Bethlehem community, not recognizing disability as a form of illness or problem that needs to be solved

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– No

Notes: Some believe that impaired reproduction is the result of political issues like excessive tear gas use, but this is not a divine punishment

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Done primarily by high God

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Many believe in angels (or jin) and that they bless and protect the community

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Rewards for loving one's neighbor, especially neighbors who are "musakeen" (poor, needy) are rewarded. This encourages such behavior.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

Notes: Selfishness is not a commonly discussed vice in this community. Members tend to succeed when they align their self-interest with their group's, often finding creative ways of doing so.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Afterlife rewards are not commonly discussed, but are commonly believed in.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Notes: As stated above, members do not explicitly endorse a belief in reincarnation. If they do believe this, they hold it privately.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– I don't know

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– No
Notes: Supernatural rewards in this life are occasionally given out, but not frequently emphasized.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes
Notes: Good luck is a possible reward, but not guaranteed. Good fortune is often seen as a sign of God's favor, indicating reward (not the reverse). For example, if an organization is able to expand its facilities or start offering new services, they often give praise to God and thank God for God's favor for them.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– No
Notes: Many in these groups express disdain for politics, often being caught in the midst of and harmed by broader political issues. For example, centers generally close on strike days (resulting when someone is killed by Israeli forces). Elections can cause chaos in the community in general, creating challenges for these organizations.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: Most believe the Messiah came once and will return again at an unknown time/ date. See Matthew 24, for example.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Messiah is expected to bring peace to the earth, including political peace.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Messiah will clarify proper religious traditions/ observances

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Equity among peoples

Notes: Among other things, the Messiah is expected to bring proper recognition to people with disabilities, such that they flourish in communal understanding and acceptance.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Notes: The day of the eschaton is unknown; it could be near or far but it is unspecified and not a frequent topic of discussion in this group.

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

Notes: There is an understanding that in the next life, all people will be treated well and with equality. Making this world like the next as much as possible is important, but not understand as causally bringing about the world's end.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: In the new world order, the Kingdom of God will reign fully. See Revelation 22, Isaiah 65, Matthew 24.

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

Notes: Rather than a new religious system, the Kingdom of God will rule in spirit and truth (John 4)

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: This is the hope of the religious group.

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, group members are expected to create positive, high-energy atmospheres. One should not explicitly refer to work as burdensome or tiresome, as that would contradict the group value of disability inclusion

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

Notes: Many of the social norms in this group are unspoken. It is an honor-shame culture, so members are expected to internalize many norms. Prompt attendance, willingness to help beyond what is explicitly required, and flexibility are all examples of common conventional norms.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: This group exists within a broader world of moral/ religious norms, but does not endorse them. Because of the religious diversity in the group, space is created for individuals to observe their holidays through, for example, vacation time and space for fasting, but these expectations are not enforced.

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Notes: Foreigners are often exempt from moral norms here, as they are understood to come from a different culture. The value of hospitality tends to be greater than enforcing such norms.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– No

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: This is a prized virtue in these communities. It applies to all members regardless of ability/ disability.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: Generosity particularly with regard to time more than money. Many organizations depend on the charity of external organizations, often international and church-based.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: Selflessness is valued implicitly, but few individuals proclaim the merits or importance of selfishness, preferring to express sacrifices as freely given for the good of the group which includes the good of the individual giver.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– No

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– No

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Notes: It is important in these organizations to treat each other with respect. Hitting, cursing, and other forms of disrespect are frequently discouraged.

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: Members are discouraged from criticizing their families of origin in this group. Family maintains priority and the first place of one's loyalty, even as these groups come to resemble second families.

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Notes: Consistency is key. Members are expected to attend regularly (daily) and to be loyal to

this group above most other groups besides one's family

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Notes: Most organizations work together to create something that can be sold (wool products, olive wood crafts, etc.)-- cooperation is key to group success.

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Notes: Most organizations try to help their members live more independently through skill development

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Notes: Neither valued nor disvalued

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Notes: Modesty in dress is expected. Humility is neither valued nor discouraged.

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Notes: Members are encouraged to seek contentment in their current circumstances

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Encouraged but not required.

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: Hope more than optimism. Many maintain a strong sense of hope, even if its object and means are vague. This hope does not consist in a belief that the future will surely or likely improve, nor warm feelings, but in consistency in action/ perseverance to bring about a better world, especially for people with disabilities, through work opportunities and general social understanding/ inclusion.

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Meals are often begun with a song of thanksgiving (often in general, rather than for specific things). Members often thank each other for help, and benefactors for their support.

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– No

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– No

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– No

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– No

Notes: While practically useful, and often depended on, this is not a group value encouraged among members.

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Notes: Members are valued specifically regardless of beauty/ attractiveness.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals are encouraged to maintain regular hygiene. Spaces are cleaned daily as part fo the "end of the day" ritual.

Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Members of some L'Arche communities around the world are expected to be celibacy so as to better live with the community of people with disabilities, who are often single. But the L'Arche community in Bethlehem, like most organizations there, do not require that. Instead, people live with their families-- whether families of origin or families they marry into.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Many members fast in season, but this is not required. Catholics and Orthodox tend to fast before Christmas and Easter and on select holidays, abstaining from animal products and olive oil. Muslim members fast during Ramadan, from food and drink during daylight.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, members need to be willing and able to spend much of their time in the community. Especially on weekends, to attend meetings, trainings, or support sales of goods produced by their organization.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: See note above regarding moral norms. One ought to recognize the dignity and value of people with disabilities to be a member of this group.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: While not required, some members are criticized for their work with people disabilities. Many with disabilities are stigmatized, mocked in the streets or otherwise scorned (sadly).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: Birthday celebrations are key in-group rituals that also bring family members to the community to help them see the beauty and significance of people with disabilities.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes members with disabilities refer to employees as “mama,” affectionately. Some employees try to distinguish themselves from the “real” moms, maintaining professional boundary and relationship as peers/ friends. Others embrace the affectionate term.

Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– No

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– Yes

Notes: See note above.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Bethlehem is in the occupied Palestinian territories (oPt). There is no officially recognized state governing it. The Palestinian Authority was established after the Oslo Accords to assist in its governance but is not an internationally recognized state. Historically, Palestinian society has been comprised of large families and tribes.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: Not famine relief per say, but this group does provide food to people in need. First, some recipients of services would otherwise lack access to sufficient food. Also, at least one of the institutions comprising this group provides sandwiches to people in need on a weekly basis (at a local hospital).

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Again, not famine relief per say, but the United Nations Relief and Works Agency (UNRWA) provides support for many in need in this community, specifically refugees living in he Bethlehem area. Local churches also provide food for some in need

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: Not specifically poverty relief, but many people with disabilities live in poverty, and often families have multiple people with disabilities, contributing to their challenges making a living. Relief they provide is mostly at an individual rather than institutional level

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: See note above regarding UNRWA. There are a variety of organizations seeking to relieve poverty, for example Bethlehem's Good Shepherd society, World Vision, and Catholic Relief Services.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: No, this is an under-cared for group in Bethlehem. Generally, people who are elderly or "infirm" live with their families and their families take care of them. However, there are some who lack family for various reasons, who struggle to receive adequate and consistent care. Such care is beyond the purview of this religious group.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Minimally, through families. See note above.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: The group does not provide formal education, but many organizations within it offer alternative education, like tutoring or individualized lessons, through the volunteers that come, either from abroad or from local universities in fulfillment of their practicum requirement. Lessons can include, English, drawing, life skills, emotional awareness, etc.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: Many people with disabilities growing up in this area struggle to receive adequate formal education. Public schools are generally inaccessible for people with mobility impairments and learning differences. Private schools are more likely to offer inclusive education, but is out of the price range of many of the group's adherents.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: Individual institutions have formal, internal bureaucracy's, some of which contact to international organizations (like LifeGate in Germany, Ma'an lil-Hayat in France with L'Arche International). There is no local bureaucratic institution governing this group as a whole.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Most notably, groups interact with the Palestinian Authority's (PA) bureaucracy. The PA licenses groups and allows them to expand services. In some cases, their bureaucracy makes further challenges for these organizations, and in rare instances, aids their work.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Water management is managed publicly through a coordination between the Palestinian Authority and the Government of Israel. Many Palestinians complain of water shortages, and note the significantly less amount of water they consume than their Israeli neighbors (particularly Israeli settlers living in the West Bank).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: The group often provides transportation, but not public infrastructure. Most member organizations provide buses to pick up members in need of a ride.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There are some public transportation options available theoretically, but generally lack the precision most adherents require to get to their specific institution. Assistants without mobility impairments could use them, but generally ride together. Recipients of services generally do not use public taxis as stigma about disability makes it potentially unsafe and likely uncomfortable. Private taxis are an option when needed, but too expensive to be a daily possibility.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: There is no tithe required to be in this group. Some individuals have formed a loan system where everyone pays, for example, 200 shekels each month, and one person takes home the whole sum of money (which rotates every month). This is optional but encouraged

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This is a common challenge for many adherents in this group. Members pay taxes to the Palestinian Authority. To purchase large, international goods like a car, they often pay taxes to the Palestinian Authority, Government of Israel, and perhaps the Kingdom of Jordan.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There is regular interaction with the Palestinian Authority's police force if groups take outings or field trips. In order to travel to Israel 48, groups need express and individual permission from the Government of Israel. One popular destination for this religious group is called Tabagha, a resort on the sea of Galilee run by religious for people with disabilities throughout the region. Often individuals are denied permission to travel for no known reason

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Palestinian Authority has a complicated judicial system combining both religious and secular law, as well as those laws which have been developed over the various governments that have occupied the land. Some laws currently in force date back to the Ottoman rule, British Mandate, Jordanian rule, and the Israeli occupation. Local churches play a significant role in mediating conflicts.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Just the Palestinian Authority, but this rarely comes up. It was not a feature of my fieldwork.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Again, just the complicated legal code administered by the Palestinian Authority.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Palestinian Authority is not allowed to develop its own military since it is not an officially recognized state, but it does have a police force subject to the Government of Israel. The PA theoretically protects this religious group, but many individuals in it have complaints about their lack of protection, from both domestic and international threats.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Their language is not distinct from the broader community in which they are found. They do have some unique spoken words, but they are never written.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The standard written language is Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) or "fusha" (فصحى). It is available outside of the religious group.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: They use the Gregorian calendar, but are also familiar with the Hijri calendar, though it is used significantly less.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Gregorian calendar is the standard among Christians in the region.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Produce is publically available through a daily farmers' market. Many individuals grow their own spices or at least some fruits and veggies. Many also harvest olives in October, used also for olive oil. Many of these organizations have trees and gardens on site, but their produce is insufficient to meet the group's food needs. They are, however, a fun source of some fruit.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Much food is available through local farmers' markets, but also through industrial methods. Packaged food is often shipped into the region from throughout the Western Arab world and occasionally elsewhere.

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